

Epidemiological portrait of tracheostomies in Brazil

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Abstract

Introduction: Tracheostomy, a surgical procedure commonly performed on critically ill patients who require long-term mechanical ventilation, was for many years considered by specialists to be a “scandalous” surgical intervention, a discourse that influenced the disuse of the procedure in contemporary times. The objective of this study is to show the epidemiological reality of this procedure in Brazil. **Materials and methods:** This is an observational, retrospective, aggregate, descriptive documentary study of secondary data extracted from the SUS Hospital Information System (SIH/SUS), available in the DataSUS database, referring to patients hospitalized in Brazil between 2008 and 2024, by place of residence, according to Chapter Z 93.0 of the ICD-10: Tracheostomies. **Results:** 295,056 tracheostomies were performed, of which 5,193 were mediastinal and 13,800 were transtumoral tracheostomies in the oncological context. The years with the highest volumes of procedures performed were 2014 and 2021, with 20,560 and 19,450 tracheostomies, respectively. The highest number of procedures occurred in the southeast region, with 35% of all tracheostomies performed. Respiratory diseases stand out as the ICD-10 diagnosis that led to the tracheostomy procedure, accounting for about 64% of the total, and the year 2021 showed a one-off increase in the mortality rate during the analyzed interval, which reached 26.3%. **Conclusion:** there was a progressive increase in the number of tracheostomies performed in Brazil at the beginning of the analyzed interval, followed by relative stability in the final years of the period in oncological and respiratory disease contexts, predominantly in the wealthiest region of the country (Southeast), with the majority of patients being male, aged 50 years or older. Patients with circulatory system diseases have a higher risk of mortality. This study has limitations, as there is underreporting of clinical data, and further studies are needed to validate the findings described here.

Keywords: Tracheostomy, respiratory, oncology.

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Introduction

Tracheostomy, a surgical procedure commonly performed in critically ill patients who require prolonged mechanical ventilation, consists of creating an opening in the anterior wall of the trachea to establish a new communication pathway between the respiratory tract and the external environment, through which a cannula is inserted to facilitate the individual's breathing [1,2]. This procedure promotes the externalization and fixation of the trachea to the skin of the neck, thus producing a permanent opening or fistula [3]. There are several techniques for performing a tracheostomy, the main ones being the

open technique—which requires transporting the patient to the operating room and performing anesthesia—and the percutaneous dilation technique, considered simpler than the open technique, which can be performed at the bedside and requires fewer health professionals [1]. The indications, technique, and ideal timing for the procedure remain controversial topics in the literature.

Historically, the first references to the tracheostomy procedure were found in the Rig Veda—a sacred text of Hindu medicine—dated between 1000 and 2000 BC, and in the Ebers Papyrus, from 1550 BC [4]. Despite the various historical reports of tracheostomies, for many

years the procedure was considered by experts to be a “scandalous” surgical intervention, a discourse that influenced its disuse during the contemporary period. Thus, airway management techniques have, over the years, often been the target of criticism and neglect by many scholars. In 1546, Italian physician Antonio Brassavola reintroduced the practice in humans by performing the first documented successful tracheotomy on a patient with tonsillar obstruction. It was not until 1923 that American physician Chevalier Jackson standardized the refined surgical technique, reducing tracheostomy-related mortality from 25% to approximately 2% [5,6].

Among the methods for performing percutaneous tracheostomy, the Ciaglia technique, introduced in 1985, has gained wide acceptance as an alternative to conventional surgical tracheostomy. The technique involved the sequential insertion of multiple dilators into the trachea until the selected tracheostomy tube could be placed. Since 2000, significant innovations in this method have included the development of the single dilator technique and the use of a high-pressure angioplasty balloon to create the stoma. Other percutaneous tracheostomy techniques, in contrast, have not achieved the same relevance in medical practice.

Tracheostomy can be performed electively or emergently, with the main indication being the need for prolonged mechanical ventilation, a condition commonly seen in trauma or critically ill patients. Other indications include upper airway obstruction, laryngotracheal stenosis, the need to reduce dead space—to facilitate ventilatory weaning—and the need for airway protection or access for secretion removal. In emergency clinical settings, tracheostomy is rarely performed, as cricothyroidotomy offers a faster means of securing the airway; its only real emergency indications are closed cervical trauma with fractures of the thyroid or cricoid cartilages [6,9,10].

Tracheostomy can be described as a procedure that provides several benefits to the patient, such as reduced need for sedatives, shorter stay in the intensive care unit (ICU) and hospital, easier weaning from mechanical ventilation, and the ability to speak while maintaining the airway.

This study aims to characterize the epidemiological profile of patients admitted through the Unified Health System (SUS) who underwent tracheostomy between 2008 and 2024 by analyzing their epidemiological characteristics.

Materials and Methods

This is an observational, retrospective, aggregate, and descriptive documentary study based on secondary data extracted from the SUS Hospital Information System (SIH/SUS), available in the DataSUS database, referring to patients admitted to hospitals in Brazil between 2008 and 2024, by place of residence, according to Chapter Z 93.0 of the ICD-10: Tracheostomies.

The data obtained were subsequently processed using Microsoft Excel software, in which tables and graphs referring to the collected data were constructed. These data can be verified through the TabNet and TabWin portals, at the following access link: <https://datasus.saude.gov.br/>.

To describe hospitalizations related to tracheostomies, the following variables were used: paid AIHs (Hospital Admission Authorizations), total cost, number of deaths, mortality rate, type of care, ICD-10 diagnosis, age group, sex, and race/skin color.

To calculate costs in US dollars, the exchange rate of July 4, 2024, of 5.4084 BRL/USD was used, according to the Central Bank of Brazil. Regarding ethical considerations, this study was exempted from submission to a Research Ethics Committee, as it exclusively used publicly accessible data, in accordance with current legislation. Nevertheless, the researchers followed the ethical principles

established by Resolution No. 466/2012 of the Brazilian National Health Council, ensuring confidentiality and responsible use of the analyzed information.

Results

Throughout the historical series, a total of 295,056 tracheostomies were performed in Brazil, of which 5,193 corresponded specifically to mediastinal tracheostomies and 13,800 to transtumoral tracheostomies in the oncological context. The temporal trend showed a progressive increase until 2014, when the highest volume in the series was recorded with 20,560 tracheostomies. In the following years, relative stability was observed, with a slight downward trend, until a new peak in 2021, totaling 19,450 procedures in that year. From then on, the numbers remained relatively stable in 2022, 2023, and 2024, ending the historical series with 14,875 tracheostomies. The annual average of procedures throughout the analyzed period was 14,050 tracheostomies per year.

In the regional analysis, the region with the highest number of procedures was the Southeast, accounting for 35% of all tracheostomies performed, totaling 102,555 procedures. Next came the South with 80,117, the Northeast with 75,967, the North with 18,811, and the Midwest with 17,606.

An analysis of gender distribution was also performed, revealing that male patients underwent tracheostomies more frequently, accounting for 64% of the total. When analyzing proportional lethality by gender, the mortality rate among men was 21%, while among women it was 27%. This indicates that, proportionally to the number of procedures performed, female patients had a 25% higher risk of death compared to men. It is also worth noting the mortality associated with mediastinal tracheostomy among women, which reached 29%, a percentage that exceeds the overall mortality rate observed among women undergoing tracheostomy.

In the analysis by age group, a direct relationship was observed between increasing age and the frequency of tracheostomies performed. The younger age groups—under 1 year, 1 to 4 years, and 5 to 14 years—each accounted for approximately 3% of the total procedures. The population aged 15 to 49 years represented 25% of cases, while the most represented age group was individuals aged 50 years or older, accounting for 66% of all tracheostomies performed.

In a proportional comparison of the distribution of causes by age group, 83.8% of tracheostomies performed for neoplasms occurred in individuals aged 50 years or older, while tracheostomies performed due to respiratory diseases predominated in the <1 year group, representing 76.8% of cases in this age group. Regarding mortality by age group, the mortality rate was 30.6% in individuals aged 50 years or older, 17% in the 15-49 age group, 3% in the 5-14 age group, 1.7% in the 1-4 age group, and 7.8% in the <1 year age group. Analyzing the distribution of deaths by cause among age groups, tracheostomies performed for respiratory diseases in individuals aged 50 years or older stood out, with a mortality rate of 33.3%.

Among the ICD-10 diagnoses that led to tracheostomy procedures, respiratory diseases and neoplasms stood out, accounting for 64% and 20% of the total, respectively. Next were external causes (6%), abnormal findings in clinical and laboratory tests (3%), and diseases of the circulatory system (2%). In the analysis of the mortality rate by cause, the highest rates were observed in tracheostomies for diseases of the circulatory system and abnormal clinical/laboratory findings, both with 32%. Next came tracheostomies due to external causes, with a mortality rate of 27%, followed by those due to respiratory diseases (26%) and, finally, those due to neoplasms, with a mortality rate of 10%.

There were a total of 80,616 deaths, corresponding to an overall mortality rate of 27.3%. Of these, 1,646 deaths were specifically attributed to mediastinal tracheostomies, with a mortality rate of 29%. Transtumoral tracheostomies in the oncological context accounted for 1,015 deaths, with a mortality rate of 7.4%. In the temporal evaluation, there was an upward trend in the number of deaths between 2008 and 2013, peaking in 2014, the year with the highest absolute number of deaths in the series, totaling 6,060 deaths. After this period, there was a progressive reduction interrupted by a new increase in 2021, when 5,118 deaths were recorded. In subsequent years, the numbers fell again, reaching their lowest level in 2024, with 3,327 deaths.

Figure 1: Total number of deaths from tracheostomy 2008-2024

A higher value was observed at the beginning of the series, particularly in 2008, with a rate of 33.6%. From then on, there was a downward trend over the years, with a temporary increase in 2021 (in the context of the coronavirus pandemic), when the rate reached 26.3%, followed again by a decline, ending the series in 2024 with a mortality rate of 22.36%. In the analysis of the mortality rate according to the type of care, emergency procedures had a significantly higher mortality rate, reaching 29% compared to elective procedures, which had a mortality rate of 17%.

Regarding the length of hospital stay, there was an overall average of 13 days per hospitalization. In 2008, the longest average length of stay was recorded, at 16.9 days. From then on, a progressive reduction was observed, reaching the lowest value in 2021, with an average of 9.9 days, and ending the series in 2024 with an average of 10.7 days. In the specific subset of transtumoral tracheostomies performed in the oncological context, the shortest average length of stay among the subgroups analyzed was identified, at only 4.5 days.

Figure 2: Total mortality rate by procedure type – elective, emergency, other occupational accidents and other external causes

The total expenditure was US\$49,941,393.10 spent over the historical series, resulting in an annual average of US\$2,937,140.77. The average amount paid per procedure was US\$169.20. The highest average amount paid per AIH was recorded in 2021, reaching US\$194 per tracheostomy, while the lowest occurred in 2019, with US\$143 per procedure. In the analysis by subtype, mediastinal tracheostomies

were associated with a significantly higher average cost, with an average value of \$181.53 per procedure. In contrast, transtumoral tracheostomies performed in the oncological context had the lowest average cost, at \$52.20 per procedure.

Discussion

Regarding the epidemiological profile of tracheostomies in Brazil, according to Nazario et al., between 2011 and 2020, male patients accounted for approximately 64.7% of all procedures performed in the country, demonstrating a significant prevalence in this group.¹ This trend can be explained by the fact that, in Brazil, the main causes of hospitalization in men are respiratory system diseases, which are important indications for tracheostomies [1,7]. In line with this scenario, several scientific publications have reported a male prevalence of tracheostomies. In Havana, men performed approximately 59% of all tracheostomies, and in Iran, approximately 66.1% [1,19,20]. Conditions such as acute respiratory failure are the reason why a large proportion of patients undergo tracheostomies, with respiratory diseases being the second leading cause of hospitalizations in Brazil [21,22]. Therefore, it is proposed that the predominance of males in tracheostomies in Brazil may be explained by the significant prevalence of these diseases in hospitalizations among this population group. According to a study that analyzed the epidemiological profile of male morbidity and mortality, the main cause of hospitalization among men in the country is respiratory diseases [9].

Conditions such as acute respiratory failure are the reason why a large proportion of patients undergo tracheostomies, with respiratory diseases being the second leading cause of hospitalizations in Brazil [21,22]. In this sense, it is proposed that the predominance of males in tracheostomies in Brazil may be explained by the significant prevalence of these diseases in hospitalizations among this population group. According to a study that analyzed the epidemiological profile of male morbidity and mortality, the main cause of hospitalization among men in the country is respiratory system diseases.⁹

A bibliometric analysis study reports that, during the COVID-19 pandemic, treatment for patients with severe manifestations of the disease commonly consisted of prolonged intubation and invasive mechanical ventilation. Thus, the authors state that the substantial challenges associated with ventilator weaning have resulted in the reliance on tracheostomy as a vital component of intensive care management for severely ill COVID-19 patients [12].

In 2021, a new peak in tracheostomies was observed, with 19,450 procedures performed during this period. It is therefore concluded that this sudden increase can be explained by the subsequent increase in the number of individuals infected with COVID-19 that same year. According to the Ministry of Health's Special Epidemiological Bulletin, in 2021, Brazil recorded the highest number of COVID-19 cases, hospitalizations for severe acute respiratory syndrome due to COVID-19, and deaths from the disease, with 14,575,102, 1,203,308, and 423,380, respectively [13].

The study conducted by Acetta et al. reaffirms the crucial role of disease severity at the time of tracheostomy in determining patient outcomes, highlighting that individuals with greater severity are associated with significantly higher mortality rates [14]. Thus, the specific increases in both the number of deaths and the mortality rate associated with tracheostomy observed in 2021 in Figures 1 and 2 can be attributed to COVID-19 surveillance indicators from that same year. These indicators portray a scenario of more severely affected patients, with a higher incidence of hospitalizations due to severe respiratory syndrome and confirmed deaths [13].

As emphasized by Meireles et al., intensive care units (ICUs) are fundamental components of modern medicine in healthcare services [15]. Every year, many patients are admitted to ICUs requiring mechanical ventilation (MV), which can be provided by orotracheal intubation or a tracheostomy tube. Thus, tracheostomy represents a routine procedure in the intensive care population [16]. The Southeast region had the highest number of procedures performed, accounting for approximately 35% of all tracheostomies performed in Brazil during the analyzed time period. This can be explained by the heterogeneity in the distribution of health goods and services observed in the country. Although the country has a total supply of beds similar to that of developed countries such as Canada and the United Kingdom, only 48% of these beds are part of the public system [17]. This is extremely detrimental in a country where approximately 77.59% of the population relies exclusively on the Unified Health System (SUS) [18]. Regarding ICU beds, the Southeast region stands out as the best structured [17]. The higher frequency of the procedure in the South and Southeast regions during the analyzed period can be attributed to the concentration and geographic distribution of intensive care unit beds, especially in the states of Rio de Janeiro, Espírito Santo, São Paulo, and Paraná [1,8]. This scenario is also observed in a systematic review study, in which, according to a survey conducted in 2018 by the Federal Council of Medicine (CFM), of the 5,570 Brazilian municipalities, only 532 have ICU beds, 53.4% of which are located in the Southeast region [15]. Questions arise regarding regional disparities in access to Brazilian health services. These inequities may corroborate the discrepancies between regions in the performance of procedures essential to maintaining patient health, such as those analyzed above regarding tracheostomies. Despite the reduction in mortality rates from cardiovascular diseases (CVD) observed by Malta DC et al. between 2000 and 2015, they remain the leading cause of death worldwide and in Brazil, accounting for approximately one-third of all deaths [23]. Furthermore, according to a systematic review led by Aguiar et al., they constituted the leading cause of ICU admissions in Brazil [14]. These data may suggest that the high mortality rate observed for tracheostomies performed due to circulatory system diseases, corresponding to 32%, is not interdependent with the procedural complications of tracheostomy, but rather caused by a pattern of pre-existing serious comorbidities brought on by these diseases in the Brazilian population. In 2021, the collected data highlighted an average amount paid per AIH for tracheostomy of US\$194—a peak possibly related to the inflationary context of the period. That year, Brazil recorded accumulated inflation of 10.06%, almost double the target for the year, which was 5.25% in 2021 [24]. This scenario is part of a sequence of inflationary cycles experienced by the country during and after the coronavirus pandemic [24,25]. This may have directly contributed to the increase in the costs of hospital procedures.

CONCLUSION

There was a progressive increase in tracheostomies performed in Brazil at the beginning of the analyzed period, followed by relative stability in the final years of the period in oncology and respiratory disease settings, predominantly in the wealthiest region of the country (Southeast). Patients were predominantly male, aged 50 or older. Patients with circulatory system diseases have a higher risk of mortality.

This study has limitations due to underreporting of clinical data, and further studies are needed to validate the findings described here.

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